

Synthesis and characterization of Zinc oxide nanoparticles

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Abstract— In this study, Zinc Oxide (ZnO) nanoparticles were synthesized using two distinct methods, with the goal of evaluating their structural and morphological properties. The particle size of the ZnO nanoparticles was determined using a particle size analyzer, yielding sizes of 320 nm and 559 nm for Sample No. 1 and Sample No. 2, respectively. The crystallographic analysis was performed using X-ray Diffraction (XRD), and the particle sizes were further corroborated by applying the Scherrer's formula to the XRD peaks, which supported the particle size measurements obtained from the analyzer. The XRD results also indicated that both samples contained relatively low levels of impurities, confirming the high purity of the synthesized ZnO nanoparticles. Further examination of the morphological characteristics was carried out through Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). Agglomeration was observed in Sample No. 1, as revealed by the SEM micrographs, suggesting that particle aggregation occurred during the synthesis process. In contrast, Sample No. 2 displayed a uniform morphology with no visible signs of agglomeration, indicating better dispersion and stability of the nanoparticles in this sample. These findings suggest that the synthesis method plays a significant role in controlling the particle size distribution and the extent of agglomeration, which in turn affects the overall properties of ZnO nanoparticles. The study provides insights into the optimization of ZnO nanoparticle synthesis for various applications, where both particle size and agglomeration behavior are critical factors.

Keywords— zinc, agglomeration, nanoparticle, particle size

I. INTRODUCTION

The newest, most promising, and most active field of contemporary research is "nanotechnology." The design, synthesis, and manipulation of particles with sizes ranging from 1 to 100 nm are the focus of the technology. Both individual atoms and the corresponding bulk material undergo fundamental changes in their chemical, physical, and biological characteristics within this size range. The particles' surface area-to-volume ratios are raised by their minuscule size. Recent years have seen a significant increase in interest in plant extract-based nanoparticles because of their exceptional qualities and broad range of uses in water treatment, pharmaceutical

ZnO nanomaterials have attracted a great interest in many research area due to its wide energy gap. It has a great electrical, structural and optical properties. It plays an important role in many photonic applications [1]. The nano materials ZnO is can also be used to absorb UV radiations. Zinc oxide being an inorganic compound with formula ZnO. It is insoluble in water. It appears as a white powder. Zinc oxide is used as an additive in many products such as glass, paints, food supplements, cement, rubber in car tyres, lubricants, ointments, batteries, pigments, zinc nutrients, fire retardants, etc. Zinc oxide is found in the earth's crust from a mineral called as zincites [2]. Nano means one-billionth, thus nanotechnology deals with materials measured in a billionth of a meter. A nanometer is 1/80,000 the diameter of a human hair or approximately ten hydrogen atoms wide. Nanotechnology is the science of very small things. But nanotechnology is not just involved with small things. Nanotechnology is a multi-disciplinary science. It includes knowledge from biology, chemistry, physics and other disciplines. Nano technology as the manipulation or self-assembly of individual atoms, molecules or molecular clusters into structures to create materials devices with new or vastly different properties. Zinc oxide is an inorganic compound with the formula ZnO. It usually appears as a white powder, nearly insoluble in water.

Zinc oxide, with its unique physical and chemical properties, such as high chemical stability, high electrochemical coupling coefficient, broad range of radiation absorption and high photo stability, is a multifunctional material. In materials science, zinc oxide is classified as a semiconductor in group II-VI, whose covalence is on the boundary between ionic and covalent semiconductors. A broad energy band (3.37 eV), high bond energy (60 meV) and high thermal and mechanical stability at room temperature make it attractive for potential use in electronics, optoelectronics and laser technology. The piezo- and pyroelectric properties of ZnO mean that it can be used as a sensor, converter, energy generator and photocatalyst in hydrogen production. Because of its hardness, rigidity and piezoelectric constant it is an

important material in the ceramics industry, while its low toxicity, biocompatibility and biodegradability make it a material of interest for biomedicine and in pro-ecological systems.

Zinc oxide is also called as a II-VI semiconductor as zinc belongs to 2nd group and oxygen belongs to 6th group of the periodic table. Zinc oxide semiconductor has some great properties such as high electron mobility, good transparency, wide bandgap, it has room temperature luminescence stronger, etc. The properties of zinc oxide semiconductor is used in transparent electrodes in liquid crystal displays and these are also used in heat protecting windows or energy saving. The ZnO has electronic applications. It is used as a thin film transistor and LED. [3]. Zinc oxide nanoparticles are the particles with size between 1nm to 100nm. Zinc oxide has surface area larger than its size. Zinc oxide has high catalytic activity. They are also used in sunscreens. They have a great antimicrobial property and can also be used to treat cancers. They are tiny particles and can move along the bloodstream therefore they can also be hazardous to health." [4]. Zinc oxide, ZnO is an inorganic compound also known as zincite and occurs rarely in nature, generally in a crystalline form. It is usually orange or red in color due to presence of manganese impurity.

Nanotechnology is a vast field incorporating itself in other fields like physics, chemistry, pharmaceutical sciences, material sciences, medicine and agriculture thus it is interdisciplinary. Its phenomenal results in other fields have let it to open its vast scope in agricultural field as well. According to the Directorate-General for internal policies of the European Union; precision agriculture is a farm management approach in which inter and intra-field effects on crops are measured to garner maximum productivity from available resources and to ensure sustainability, aptness and protection to the environment. Broadly nanotechnology is used in the latest agriculture to materialize the concept of precision agriculture. Nanotechnology incorporates the particles on nanoscale having diameter of 100nm [5].

The particulate diffusions or solid particles in size range of 10-1000nm are regarded as nanoparticles. To a nanoparticle matrix a drug is solvated, ensnared or cohered. It depends on method of preparation to obtain nanoparticles, Nano spheres or Nano capsules. Nano capsules are the colloidal nano bubbles in which the drug is encased to a cavity circled by a unique non-toxic polymer membrane, while Nano spheres are matrix systems of spherical shape in which physical and even distribution is ensured. Because of the potential of circulation for an elongated time period, targets a specific organ, as carriers of DNA in the gene therapy technique, and the potential to bear proteins, genes and peptides, the biodegradable polymeric nanoparticles, significantly those coated with hydrophilic polymer such as poly (ethylene glycol) (PEG) known as long-circulating particles, are used as potential drug delivery devices, over the recent years [6]. The vast diversity of applications of Nano sized metal oxide particles have dwelled them in significant consideration. In toothpaste, beauty products, sunscreens, and textiles, Titanium dioxide (TiO₂) and zinc oxide (ZnO) nanoparticles (NPs) are incorporated. Ceramic Nano-powders of metal oxides such as ZnO manifest noticeable antibacterial activity [7]. The use of metal oxides has an advantage over organic antimicrobial agents due their enhanced safety and stability [7]. Due to the larger surface area and little size of nanoparticles and distinctive optical properties they have vast applications in plant protection, nourishment and farm practices [8]. It usually appears as a white crystalline powder, which is nearly insoluble in water. Most of ZnO which is used commercially is produced synthetically. ZnO is actually a widebandgap semiconductor of the II-VI semiconductor group. The doping of the semiconductor is n-type which is due to oxygen vacancies. These properties are used in applications for electrodes in liquid crystal displays as well as in energy-saving and heat-protecting windows[8], electronic applications of ZnO as thin-film transistors and light-emitting diodes and also in ceramics plastic Zinc oxide (ZnO) has a stable wurtzite structure[9] with lattice spacing $a = 0.325$ nanometres and $c = 0.521$ nanometres. Because of its unique properties and versatile Applications, it is used in transparent electronics, ultraviolet (UV) light emitters, piezoelectric devices and chemical sensors. These remarkable physical properties form the basis for motivation of device miniaturization, large effort has been focused on the synthesis, characterization and device applications of ZnO nanomaterials.

II. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

ZnO material is been prepared here by two methods although there are many different methods to be used to prepare ZnO. These methods are very simple if compared to other methods and the materials used to prepare ZnO by these methods are very easily available.

1.1. By wet chemical method

I. Synthesis of ZnO-1

The wet chemical methods were used in which zinc nitrate and sodium hydroxides precursors are used. The soluble starch was also used as a stabilizing agent. 0.1 percent soluble starch with variable concentration were dissolved using microwave oven in 250ml of distilled water. 0.05 mol of zinc nitrate of mass 7.38g was used in the prepared solution. By the method of continuous stirring of the above solution for 1 hour with the help of magnetic stirrer in order to completely dissolve the zinc nitrate. When the zinc nitrate gets completely dissolved in the solution then 0.1 mol of 150 ml sodium hydroxide was dissolved in the above solution by constant stirring, this sodium hydroxide was added drop by drop by touching the walls of the container for 2 hours. When the reaction was complete the solution was allowed for 12 hours to get settled and the discarding of the supernant solution was done carefully. After that the centrifugation of the solution was done for 10min and then finally the supernant was discarded. The resultant nanoparticles of ZnO-1 were washed about three times using the de-ionised water (3X) and by using the ethanol (2X). We washed the nanoparticles obtained in order to remove the excessive starch and by-products that were present with them. After washing was done three times the nanoparticles of ZnO-1 were dried at 80degree Celsius for 12 hours. During the process of drying the nanoparticles obtained there was the complete conversion of Zinc hydroxide into Zinc oxide.

II. Preparation of ZnO-2

When 100ml of Zinc nitrate solution was neutralized with 250ml of sodium hydroxide to pH value of 12 the Zinc oxide was synthesized. After the completion of the above reaction the solid and liquid phase were separated by the process of centrifugation. The solid phase obtained by centrifugation were washed by de-ionised water(3X) and ethanol (2X). Then the white power obtained was heated at temperature of 80 degree Celsius and then it was grinded to get uniform white powder of zinc oxide. The dry prepared powder was measured. Its weight and percentage yields were calculated from the total amount of Zinc oxide. These calculations were based on volume of the solution and concentration of the solution and total amount that was crystallized.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

I. X- ray diffraction method

X-ray diffraction is an analytical and non-destructive technique which is versatile for determination of the different crystalline forms by quantitative approach. These different crystalline forms are know as phases. When there is interaction between waves and regular structures which have the repeated distance between the atoms same as compared to the wavelength of the wave then diffraction takes place. These diffraction phenomenon are common in the nature and keeping occurring on different levels. The diffraction of light occurs when light is incident of a surface of a material in which the inter-atomic distance is in order of angstroms which is about the wavelength of light. X-ray diffraction takes place almost in all crystalline solids because they have inter-atomic distance about the wavelength of the X-rays. Therefore diffraction occurs in the materials which are having crystalline nature and with regular repeated atomic structure. In 1911 Bragg found a relation between many quantities. The growth mechanism of ZnO nanostructures is influenced by the existence of surfactant as cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) in the solution. In the presence of surfactant, the

surface tension of solution is decreased which minimizes the surface energy to form a ZnO nanocrystals. Being an ionic compound, the CTAB completely ionizes in water and forms a positively charged tetrahedron with a long hydrophobic tail, while the Zn(OH)_4^{2-} is considered to be grown for ZnO crystal which has a negatively charged tetrahedron geometry. The chemical reaction between the surface of ZnO nuclei and the ions produced by the ionization of capping material gives rise to the formation of different morphology. In Fig.1 and Fig.2 highest peaks are seen at a same angle of 36.48 degrees so, we can roughly say that these two samples were same.

Fig. 1 XRD of ZnO Sample No.1

Fig. 2 XRD of ZnO Sample No.2

II. Scanning electron microscope (SEM)

The scanning electron microscope produces various signals at the surfaces of solid specimens by Focusing beam of electrons with high energy on the surface of solid specimen. The information about the sample and its external morphology is obtained by the signals produced by these interactions between sample and electrons. These interactions also reveal texture, crystalline structure, chemical composition and the orientations. The data is been collected by taking a small part on the surface of the sample under investigation and the two dimensional image is produced that shows spatial difference in these properties. With the help of SEM we can study the areas of sample of approximately 1cm to 5 microns in width by conventional SEM methods these samples can be viewed in scanning mode by these techniques of SEM(magnification of 20X to 30000X, resolution of 50 to 100nm). The SEM analysis of the ZnO-1 and ZnO-2 samples organized from two unique strategies became done via SEM (JEOL-JSM 5800). The micrographs are shown above. Fig.3 indicates that there is some network type structure formed of the ZnO-1 . It simply shows that there the agglomeration has occurred. Similarly, in fig. 4 a big aggregation of the pattern ZnO-2 particles has been taken region. It isn't possible to are expecting the precise size of the character particle, which can be completed via TEM evaluation. From the micrograph, it may be guessed that the particles are abnormal in form, however for the size of the debris, particle analyzer become done similarly.

Fig. 3 SEM of ZnO Sample No.1

Fig. 4 SEM of ZnO Sample No.2

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Zinc Oxide (ZnO) nanoparticles were synthesized using two distinct methods, with the goal of evaluating their structural and morphological properties. The particle size of the ZnO nanoparticles was determined using a particle size analyzer, yielding sizes of 320 nm and 559 nm for Sample No. 1 and Sample No. 2, respectively. The crystallographic analysis was performed using X-ray Diffraction (XRD), and the particle sizes were further corroborated by applying the Scherrer's formula to the XRD peaks, which supported the particle size measurements obtained from the analyzer. The XRD results also indicated that both samples contained relatively low levels of impurities, confirming the high purity of the synthesized ZnO nanoparticles. Zinc oxide is a multifunctional material because of its many interesting properties (piezo- and pyroelectric), a wide range of UV absorption, and high photostability, biocompatibility and biodegradability. ZnO can also be obtained with a variety of particle structures, which determine its use in new materials and potential applications in a wide range of fields of technology. Zinc oxide nanoparticles were synthesized by different methods such as wet chemical method, sol-gel method, green leaf extract method, microwave and hydrothermal methods and the prepared nanoparticles were characterized by XRD and SEM. The crystallite size of the prepared zinc oxide nanoparticles varies from 25- 30 nm. All the prepared nanoparticles showed wurtzite structure. SEM analysis, suggested different morphological structures from flower like arrangement to spherical shape. Crystalline oxide powders, combined with other materials, provide possibilities for obtaining improved chemical, mechanical, optical or electrical properties.

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